

Formatted Curriculum

Supplementary Material for Master Thesis: Development of a
Master-level Program for Green Coding: A Curriculum Design and
Implementation Approach

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Introduction: This file contains a course overview of all courses proposed for the Green Coding program in the aforementioned Master thesis. The template explored within the thesis was used for this curriculum overview, containing essential, compact information about the individual courses.

1 Basic Courses

Title	Sustainability and Software
Scope	5 credits
Learning Objective	Teach fundamental knowledge about human effects on the environment, raise awareness on the importance of earth preservation and sustainability in general.
Required Previous Courses	-
Format	Lectures
Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. History of Sustainability<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Limits to Growthb) Our Common Futurec) Triple Bottom Line2. Current Approaches to Sustainability<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Five Dimensions of Sustainability (Karlskrona Manifesto)b) Sustainable Development Goals3. Facets of Human–Environment–Interaction<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Emissions and Greenhouse Gasesb) Resource Depletionc) Energy Efficiencyd) Waste and Disposal4. Environmental Impacts<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Life Cycle Assessmentb) Impact Assessmentc) First-, Second-, Third-Order Effects5. Impacts of Computer Science and Software Engineering<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Hardware: E-Waste, Resource Consumptionb) Software: Resource Consumption6. Current World Status<ol style="list-style-type: none">a) Earth Overshoot Dayb) Current State of Climate Change

Suggested Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meadows et. al (1972): <i>The Limits to Growth: A Report to The Club of Rome</i> - World Commission on Environment and Development (1987): <i>Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development – Our Common Future</i> - John Elkington (1998): <i>Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business</i> - Becker et. al (2015): <i>Sustainability Design and Software: The Karlskrona Manifesto</i> - World Resources Institute and World Business Council for Sustainable Development (2015): <i>The Greenhouse Gas Protocol</i>
Examination Type	Quiz

Table 1: Curriculum: Sustainability and Software

Title	Introduction to Green Coding
Scope	5 credits
Learning Objective	Give fundamental definitions and overview of Green IT and Green Coding as a basis for further courses.
Required Previous Courses	-
Format	Lectures, Simulation Tasks

Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Definitions and Delineations <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Green IT b) Green by IT c) Green Coding 2. Extent of Green Coding <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Software b) Hardware c) Software Development Life Cycle d) Green Software Ecosystems 3. Industrial Relevance of Green Coding 4. Sustainability Assessment Overview <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Impediments when Measuring Sustainability b) Software Carbon Intensity c) Guidelines of Blue Angel for Software d) GREENSOFT Framework e) Software Sustainability Analysis Framework
Suggested Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taina (2011): <i>Good, Bad, and Beautiful Software – In Search of Green Software Quality Factors</i> - Naumann et. al (2011): <i>The GREENSOFT Model: A Reference Model for Green and Sustainable Software and its Engineering</i> - Gröger et. al (2018): <i>Entwicklung und Anwendung von Bewertungsgrundlagen für ressourceneffiziente Software unter Berücksichtigung bestehender Methodik</i> - Noman et. al. (2024): <i>Towards Sustainable Software Systems: A Software Sustainability Analysis Framework</i> - Nouredine (2024): <i>Observing and Understanding Green Software Ecosystems</i>
Examination Type	Quiz, Sustainability Assessment Task

Table 2: Curriculum: Introduction to Green Coding

2 Advanced Courses

Title	Green Computing
Scope	5 credits
Learning Objective	Familiarize students with theory and practical use of green computing practices.
Required Previous Courses	Introduction to Green Coding
Format	Lectures, Coding Tasks
Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Definition and Extent of Green Computing 2. Deep Dives at Micro Level (Developer Practices) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sustainable Software Design and Architectures b) Energy-efficient Programming Languages and Algorithms c) Green Data Transfer and API Usage d) Web Development e) Green AI 3. Deep Dives at Macro Level (Infrastructure Focus) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sustainability for Data Centers b) Green Networking c) Load Balancing d) Cloud Computing
Suggested Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pereira et. al. (2017): <i>Energy Efficiency across Programming Languages</i> - Corral-García et. al. (2019): <i>Analysis of Energy Consumption and Optimization Techniques for Writing Energy-Efficient Code</i> - Paul et. al. (2023): <i>A Comprehensive Review of Green Computing: Past, Present, and Future Research</i> - Naumann et. al. (2020): <i>The Eco-label Blue Angel for Software—Development and Components</i> - Guldner (2025): <i>Assessing the Resource and Energy Efficiency of Software and Artificial Intelligence Systems</i>

Examination Type	Coding Tasks
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Table 3: Curriculum: Green Computing

Title	Green Software Development Life Cycle
Scope	5 credits
Learning Objective	Broaden view on software development by showing holistic life cycle of the software engineering and development process.
Required Previous Courses	Sustainability and Software, Introduction to Green Coding
Format	Lectures, Simulation Tasks
Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The SDLC: Different Approaches <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Requirements Engineering b) Design c) Implementation d) Testing and Maintenance e) Evolution and End of Life 2. GREENSOFT Approach in Detail 3. Green Requirements Engineering 4. Agile Models and Green SCRUM 5. Sustainable DevOps

Suggested Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Naumann et. al (2011): <i>The GREENSOFT Model: A Reference Model for Green and Sustainable Software and its Engineering</i> - Dick et. al. (2013): <i>Green Software Engineering with Agile Methods</i> - Penzenstadler et. al. (2014): <i>Safety, Security, Now Sustainability: The Nonfunctional Requirement for the 21st Century</i> - Mahaux et. al. (2015): <i>Integrating the Complexity of Sustainability in Requirements Engineering</i> - David (2025): <i>SusDevOps: Promoting Sustainability to a First Principle in Software Delivery</i>
Examination Type	LCA Project on Software Product

Table 4: Curriculum: Green SDLC

Title	Awareness and Sustainability in Human-Computer Interaction
Scope	5 credits
Learning Objective	Sharpen senses of students on importance of sustainability, accessibility, and end user integration into software design choices.
Required Previous Courses	Sustainability and Software
Format	Lectures

Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Main Issues in Modern, Digitized Life <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Lacking Awareness of Effects of Soft- and Hardware Usage b) Rebound Effects c) Longevity and Hardware Obsolescence d) Digital Well-Being and Sobriety 2. Software Quality (based on ISO 25010) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Sustainability as Non-Functional Requirement b) Usability and Accessibility c) Inspecting Accessibility 3. Inspecting Sustainability as an End User <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Usage Patterns and Their Effects b) Green Feedback
Suggested Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hilty et. al. (2011): <i>Sustainability and ICT – An Overview of the Field</i> - Lago et. al. (2015): <i>Framing Sustainability as a Property of Software Quality</i> - Kern et. al. (2015): <i>Labelling Sustainable Software Products and Websites: Ideas, Approaches, and Challenges</i> - Nouredine et. al. (2023): <i>The Impact of Green Feedback on Users' Software Usage</i> - ISO (2023): <i>ISO/IEC 25010:2023 – Systems and Software Engineering — Systems and Software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) — Product Quality Model</i>
Examination Type	Learning Journal

Table 5: Curriculum: Awareness and Sustainability in HCI

Title	Sustainability and Governance in Companies
Scope	5 credits

Learning Objective	Ensuring students know the importance of sustainability in companies and how to propagate it, including relevant laws and standards.
Required Previous Courses	Sustainability and Software
Format	Lectures, Case Studies
Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Main Issues Regarding Sustainability in Companies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Financial Aspects b) Greenwashing c) Impact of Companies on Environment 2. Integrating Changes into Companies <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Change Management b) Resilience Training 3. Overview on Regulations and Standards <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Carbon Footprint b) EU ETS c) Clean Air Act d) GRI e) ESG Reporting f) AI Act g) Labels (e.g., Blue Angel) 4. Case Studies on Start-Ups and Established Companies
Suggested Literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kern et. al. (2015): <i>Impacts of Software and its Engineering on the Carbon Footprint of ICT</i> - Arslan (2021): <i>Ecological Sustainability in Software Development</i> - Chowdhury et. al. (2021): <i>Understanding Change Management in Organizational Context: Revisiting Literature</i> - Lill-Kochems (2024): <i>Green Coding für junge Softwareunternehmen</i> - Ketelaars et. al. (2024): <i>Resilience Training for Critical Situation Management</i>

Examination Type	Case Study
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Table 6: Curriculum: Sustainability and Governance in Companies

Title	Current Trends in Green Coding
Scope	5 credits
Learning Objective	Ensuring students have the competency to analyse scientific papers independently in order to stay up to date in the evolving field of Green Coding.
Required Previous Courses	Introduction to Green Coding
Format	Literature Review, Presentations
Contents	Identification of current trends through up-to-date literature reviews and student presentations.
Suggested Literature	–
Examination Type	Presentation

Table 7: Curriculum: Current Trends in Green Coding

3 Practical Application

Title	Green Coding in Practice
Scope	10 credits
Learning Objective	Walk through a full Software Engineering process infused with Green Coding principles to ensure students develop practical sustainability skills.

Required Previous Courses	Sustainability and Governance in Companies, Green SDLC, Awareness and Sustainability in HCI, Green Computing
Format	Project
Contents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Create Fictional Company 2. Assign Roles in Agile SE Process 3. Assess Status Quo 4. Create Software Product Through All Stages of Green SDLC 5. Ensure Integration and Training of Software in Company 6. Inspect Software as an End User
Suggested Literature	–
Examination Type	Project

Table 8: Curriculum: Green Coding in Practice